

Review Article

Malaria, Antimalarials And the Rising Spate of Antimalarial Resistance in Nigeria: A Global Threat

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Abstract

Malaria is an endemic disease prevalent in the sub-Saharan Africa region, South-East Asia and the East Mediterranean regions. In 2023, there was an estimated 263 million malaria cases and 597,000 deaths globally with the African region bearing the largest share of the disease. Nigeria had a huge share of the disease at 27% of the total estimate. Hence, the use of antimalarials in the treatment of this menace in Nigeria cannot be underemphasized. There are increased malaria parasite cases, most fevers are attributed to malaria and over the counter self-medication is on the rise; these reports have given rise to antimalarial/microbial resistance which is becoming of global public health concern. Journals from 2014- 2025 related to the spread of antimalarial resistance (AMR) were gotten from public databases using Google scholar and PubMed. The search was made using key words like “malaria”, “antimalarials”, “antimalarial resistance”, “One health approach”, “antimalarial abuse in Nigeria”. Out of 178 articles providing details on these topics singly or in combination were filtered and used for building up this review work, fifty were referenced. This review was also used to provide the overview of the growing issue of AMR in Nigeria and how it can affect the global community. This study captures malaria, different antimalarials used, their mechanism of actions and the genetic markers used for the detection of malaria especially the drug-resistant parasites. Early testing, treatment with quality antimalarials, environmental cleanliness and enlightenment campaigns on malaria and drug resistance is advocated to prevent emergence of resistant strains of *Plasmodium falciparum*. Validation and verification of different tests kits used for identification should be carried out to ensure accuracy and reliability of the reagents and kits used. The use of antimalarials and antibiotics should be regulated and used only when needed. Education on preventive measures, compliance when on treatment with antimalarials and enlightenment campaigns should be encouraged to eliminate malaria.

1. Introduction

Malaria is an endemic disease particularly common in the World Health Organization African Region. It causes febrile illness that presents with chills, fever, headache and malaise it can become severe if not treated appropriately leading to convulsions, acute renal damage, coma and death. Nigeria bears the highest burden of the disease accounting for almost 27% of global malaria cases and 31% of malaria deaths [1]. The entire population is at risk but children and pregnant mothers are more prone to the disease due to their weakened immunity at the time [2, 3]. Of all the infectious diseases, malaria is the second deadliest in Africa and the leading cause of death in Nigeria after HIV-AIDS [4–6].

Nigeria is the most populous developing West African country located in the *Plasmodium*-endemic areas with 237.5 million inhabitants and sixth most populous in the world [7]. The gross domestic product (GDP) in US dollars (USD) rose to 3.13% in 2025 from 2.27% estimated to be about \$188.27 billion USD [8, 9]. It carries the world's highest malaria burden and this causes a significant public health burden. In 2021, there was an estimated 68million cases and 194,000 deaths in the African region accounting for 27% of the global malaria burden [10]. Its diverse ecological zones, including the Sahel region in the North, the Sudan savannah and the rainforest in the South play a significant role in shaping the transmission dynamics of malaria and the whole population is at risk [11]. The data published by the WHO show that the number of new cases increases year by year [10]. Malaria has significant economic and health consequences costly over USD\$1.1 billion annually and accounting for 60% of all hospital visits in Nigeria [12].

Antimalarial drugs commonly used for treatment of malaria were the chloroquine (4-aminoquinoline) which were the gold standard treatment for uncomplicated malaria for many years but now not as effective as drug resistance has overtaken it. Artemisinin-based combination therapies (ACTs) were later used for treating uncomplicated *falciparum* malaria in all regions and also for chloroquine resistant *P. vivax* malaria [13]. The irrational and overuse of antimalarials is currently on the rise in the African region partly because some of the antimalarials been used now are not very effective or that there are resistant strains of the parasite just as seen in some bacterial infections having resistant strains of bacteria. Antimalarial resistance can occur when the body does not respond to antimalarial treatment in the usual dosage that should bring about therapeutic effect. The use of antimalarials is indispensable in treating malaria, there have been reports of repeated cases of the disease even after treatment which encourages self-medications especially in the African regions where drugs can be bought over the counter. The underuse, overuse or misuse of antimicrobials can lead to extended antimicrobial resistance wherein the environment acts as a reservoir of antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs), completing the cycle of contamination and recontamination [14], this is also the case for irrational use of antimalarials which is commonly seen now in our clime. The rise of poor-quality drugs especially in Nigeria and other developing world that depend on importation from other climes for active ingredients poses a threat to production of quality drugs. Antimicrobial /antimalarial resistance (AMR) effect can have a multi-faceted approach affecting humans, animals and the environment i.e. the One-health approach; so, any policy by government to reduce the burden of AMR will reduce health risks on humans, animals and the environment. Therefore, antimalarials being used should be of quality products with active pharmaceutical ingredients, can be indigenously produced with our genetic markers being targeted appropriately. So, the right drug and right dosage is important for malaria control and elimination programs to be effective so that the growing trend of antimalarial resistance will be curbed considering its endemicity in our region.

Another wake-up call is the 2025 World Malaria Day with the theme “Malaria ends with Us: Reinvest, Reimagine, reignite”, emphasizing the need for continued investment, innovation, collaboration and commitment from the global malaria eradication community cascading action from global policies to community action hence ensuring progress towards malaria elimination through right testing, treatment and control strategies [15]. The objective of this review is to find out the studies on malaria, antimalarials and the relationship it has with AMR. This study will provide information that is essential in policy making and implementation in the fight against malaria and the role antimalarial resistance genes can play in bringing about insensitivities in drugs against malaria.

1.1. Epidemiology of common Antimalarials and emergence of antimalarial resistance

Antimalarial resistance viz a viz antimicrobial resistance according to the World Health Organization “is the ability of a parasite strain (microorganism) to survive and/or multiply despite the administration and absorption of medicine given in doses equal to or higher than those usually recommended but within the tolerance of the subject, provided drug exposure at the site of action is adequate [16, 17].” This resistance can be caused by change in structure, function or quantity of a protein. Genetic changes can be caused by gene amplification or single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNP) [18]. Parasites are mutating continuously so the generation of new molecules to overcome this challenge is paramount. Copy number variations in *Pfmdr1*, *Pfcr1*, *Pfmdr1* sequence variants can affect the parasite's susceptibility making it not prone to the drugs used [17, 19, 20]. The uniqueness of the parasite resistance mechanism makes it possible to be able to induce resistance in the particular drug target it is meant to work upon unlike other diseases like tuberculosis and AIDS [21].

The *Plasmodium* species (*falciparum*, *ovale*, *malariae*, *knowlesi*) cause malaria. *Plasmodium falciparum* is endemic in the sub-Saharan region and the most virulent of the other species causing the most dangerous of sequelae if not treated promptly. The climate and environmental conditions make the vector female *Anopheles gambiae* and *Anopheles funestus* prone to the African region. Studies show that malaria is caused more by man-made water bodies/puddles which were greater than natural waterbodies in breeding these mosquitoes [22, 23]. Antimalarial drugs are used to treat and prevent malaria infection; they are key tools in control and elimination of malaria. Based on the mechanism of action, antimalarial drugs are mainly classified into three groups: quinolone, antifolate and artemisinin derivatives [19]. The quinolones-chloroquines (CQ) were synthetic antimalarial drugs used to treat, prevent and eradicate ‘mal’ ’aria’ (bad air, related to its origination from swampy environments) in the 1940s. “Chloroquine-resistant *P. falciparum* first developed independently in three to four areas in Southeast Asia, Oceania, and South America in the late 1950s and early 1960s. Since then, chloroquine resistance has spread to nearly all areas of the world where *falciparum* malaria is transmitted” [24]. Also, close to the 1980s, the eradication programs waned and malaria deaths increased due to the resistance of the parasites to CQ [2, 19]. But for *Plasmodium vivax* treatment, chloroquine remains the first line of treatment [25]. Chloroquine plus primaquine used as first-line regime for treating *vivax* malaria in most areas, atovaquone-proguanil (Malarone), mefloquine and doxycycline are recommended for travellers from non-endemic malaria regions to endemic regions so used as chemoprophylactic regimens Also, primaquine phosphate which acts against gametocytes thereby lowering transmission of parasites to mosquito vectors [17].

The antifolates which block the parasite's enzymes (dihydrofolate reductase e.g. in sulfadoxine/pyrimethamine (SP), proguanil) were then used as first line of treatment for malaria to replace CQ, but resistance also spread globally [17]. It was seen that the long-term use of monotherapy during malaria treatment has resulted in drug resistance.

Since 2001, the WHO has recommended the use of artemisinin-based combination therapy (ACT) in countries facing the resistance problem [26]. The use of combination therapies was advocated for, instead of monotherapy to increase the efficacy of the drugs and reduce the emergence of drug-resistant parasites which led to the use of artemisinin-based combination therapies (ACT). The ACTs recommended by the WHO are artemether/lumefantrine (AL), artesunate/amodiaquine, artesunate/mefloquine, dihydroartemisinin/piperazine, artesunate/pyronaridine, and artesunate/sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (A/SP) [16, 27]. ACTs are also effective against erythrocytic stages of

non-falciparum malaria parasites [16]. But even recently, resistance to artemisinin have been reported in Nigeria, Southeast Asia increasing global alarm for malaria treatment and control [16, 27].

According to the Center for Disease Control and Prevention, *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* are the two species out of the four human malaria parasite species (*Plasmodium malariae*, *Plasmodium ovale*) confirmed to have grown resistance to currently available antimalarial drugs [24].

The World Health Organization (WHO) does not recommend chemoprophylaxis in African residents but alternative strategies like: intermittent preventive treatment in pregnant women, also in infants; (IPTp and IPTi) and seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) in young children living in the Sahel region [16]. From 2021, the WHO also recommended the RTS, S/AS01 (Mosquirix®) malaria vaccine manufactured by GlaxoSmithKline (GSK) to prevent *P. falciparum* malaria in children living in areas with moderate-to-high malaria transmission [16].

Early testing to confirm the presence of the parasite, the right drug at the right time and compliance by the patient is key in preventing AMR. Antimalarial drugs should serve to clear malaria parasites in positive cases; be safe especially in children and pregnant mothers, address drug resistance challenges; in public health perspective antimalarials with poor quality, little or no active pharmaceutical ingredients (API) may cause increased morbidity and mortality [28]. Drugs with low quality (API) or low bioavailability may be selected by drug-resistant parasites [29]. This leads to great economic loss for patients and families, healthcare system and the community even the companies producing the genuine products are at risk of not getting the right market [30].

1.2. Mechanism of action of antimalarials and their molecular markers

The life cycle of malaria is a complicated one involving three stages, the erythrocytic stage, the liver stage (exo-erythrocytic stage) and the asexual stage in the mosquito. Generally, when the mosquito takes a blood meal, the parasites are deposited, then develop to trophozoites, enlarge to form the merozoites which matures to release schizonts carrying the daughter cells, some go through the exo-erythrocytic cycle as hypnozoites while others go through the asexual stage to perpetuate the cycle [14, 31]. The mechanism of action of antimalarial drugs work to inhibit any of the cycles to prevent the symptoms of malaria. While most of the antimalarials target the asexual blood stages of the parasite, primaquine targets the hypnozoites [19]. The common antimalarials and their actions are as follows:

Table 1: Antimalarials and their Mechanisms of action [19, 28, 32]

Antimalarial derivatives	Chemical family	Drug name	Mechanism of action	Use	Genetic markers for drug resistance
Quinolone derivatives	4-aminoquinolones	Chloroquine	Accumulation in the digestive vacuole of parasite and inhibition of heme detoxification	Treatment of non-falciparum infections, treatment of falciparum malaria where chloroquine is sensitive	Point mutation in <i>Pfcr1</i> , <i>Pfmdr1</i> , <i>Pfmrp</i>
		Amodiaquine	Accumulation in the digestive vacuole of parasite and inhibition of heme detoxification	Treatment of non-severe falciparum infections where chloroquine resistance has emerged	Point mutation and copy number variation in <i>Pfmdr1</i>
	Amino alcohols	Quinine, Mefloquine, Halofantrine and Lumefantrine	Accumulation in the digestive vacuole of the parasite and inhibition of heme detoxification	Treatment of severe malaria and multidrug resistant falciparum infections	Point mutation in <i>Pfmdr1</i> , <i>Pfmrp</i> , and copy number variation in <i>Pfmdr1</i>
	8-aminoquinolones	Primaquine	Not precisely known	Treatment of vivax and ovale infections to prevent relapse. Gametocytocidal agent	Not known
Antifolate derivatives	Naphthoquinone	Atovaquone	Targets the cytochrome bc1 complex located in the inner mitochondrial membrane of parasite. Inhibits respiratory reaction of parasite	Treatment of multidrug resistant falciparum malaria infections	Point mutation in <i>cytb</i> gene
	Sulfa drugs	Sulfadoxine, Sulfene	Inhibits the dihydropteroate synthetase enzyme (PDHPS). Inhibition of folate biosynthesis	Treatment of non-severe infections in combination with Pyrimethamine where chloroquine resistance has emerged	Point mutation in <i>Pfdhps</i>
	Pyrimethamine, Proguanil	Pyrimethamine, Proguanil	Inhibits the dihydrofolate reductase (PDHFR) activity. Inhibition of folate biosynthesis		Point mutation in <i>Pfdhfr</i>
Artemisinin derivatives	Endoperoxides	Artesunate	Not clear but a heme mediated breakdown of endoperoxide bridge releasing carbon centered free radicals lethal to the parasite.	Treatment of multidrug-resistant falciparum malaria infections. Combination with other drugs to prevent drug resistance	Polymorphism in Kelch 13 protein
	Antibiotics		Tetracycline	Inhibitors of protein synthesis pathway	Combination with quinine increase efficacy of treatment where quinine resistance has emerged or reduce the likelihood of quinine related side effects by reducing duration of quinine treatment
		Doxycycline	Inhibit the binding of aminoacyl tRNA to the mRNA ribosomal complex	Prophylaxis	
		Clindamycin	Inhibitors of protein synthesis	For non-immune patients unable to take tetracycline. In combination with quinine, can increase the efficacy of treatment where quinine resistance has emerged and reduce the likelihood of side effects of quinine treatment.	

1.3. The Genetic Markers of Drug resistance

Genetic markers of drug resistance are important indices used to identify the emergence and spread of drug resistance globally. Genetic crosslink and mapping studies of parasites are used in identifying these genetic markers. Molecular analyses showed mutation in the *P.falciparum* chloroquine resistance transporter (*Pfcr1*) gene that correlates well with chloroquine susceptible and resistant strains in both laboratory and field isolates [33]. Antifolate drugs, Sulfadoxine Pyrimethamine (SP), inhibits *P.falciparum* dihydropteroate synthetase (*PfDHPS*) and *P.falciparum* bifunctional dihydrofolate reductase thymidylate synthase (*PfDHFR*) enzyme involved in the parasite folate biosynthesis pathway but there have been mutations seen in these genes using genetic cross linkage and biochemical studies that have reduced the susceptibility of the SP drugs [19, 34]. Resistance in the artemisinin-drug was shown by whole genome sequencing that identified mutation in the Kelch13 (K13) propeller protein associated with artemisinin resistance in clinical and field isolate samples which reduced efficacy of the drugs leading to resistance to this current known antimalarial [32, 35, 36].

The *P.falciparum* chloroquine resistant transporter gene (*Pfcr1*) is the most reliable molecular marker of chloroquine resistance (CQR) and also found to be associated with resistance to other drugs like piperazine [37]. The gene responsible for the chloroquine (CQ) resistance *Pfcr1* have been found to have variations which influences antimalarial drug susceptibility and resistance to quinine, amodiaquine (AQ), piperazine and lumefantrine. Mutations were common in the K76T region and was the main determinant of CQ resistance and susceptibility. Other sites like C72S, M74I, N75E, A220S, Q271E, N326S, I356T, and R371 also conferred resistance but only in association with K76T mutation [19]. CQ-resistant variants showed decreased affinity to C, this led to less accumulation of CQ in the digestive vacuole giving rise to CQ resistance [38]. K76T mutation in *Pfcr1* protein is seen to be a potent molecular marker for the quinolone derivatives antimalarial drug, depending on their previous use in the region (mutations on codons 72-76 was seen to have higher resistance to CQ and medium level resistance in Southeast Asia and Africa but linked with greater AQ resistance in South America) [32, 39].

The polymorphism of the Kelch 13 propeller gene in *P.falciparum* (*PfK13*) has been found to be the molecular marker of partial resistance of ART. K13 mutation leads to decreased sensitivity of *Plasmodium* to artemisinin by blocking the activation of artemisinin thereby enhancing the antioxidant effect of malaria parasites, decreasing the damage of proteins and promoting the repair of DNA damage, thus the malaria parasite enhances DNA repair when K13 mutation occurs [32]. During the growth and development of red blood cells, *Plasmodium* takes in hemoglobin and utilizes amino acids. The breakdown of hemoglobin produces heme, which plays an important role in the activation of artemisinin. The K13 protein is related to the endocytosis of hemoglobin by the malaria parasite. *PfK13* mutation reduces the endocytosis of hemoglobin and the activation of artemisinin, resulting in decreased sensitivity to artemisinin [40]. Other non-kelch 13 genes like *Pfcoronin* mutants were also found to cause artemisinin resistance in Nigeria by blocking the activity of artemisinin thus reducing the artemisinin effect on the parasite [41]. Mutations in *Plasmodium falciparum* multidrug resistance protein 1 (*Pfmdr1*) gene at the following positions (N86Y, Y184F, S1034C, N1042D, and D1246Y) have been reported to be involved in determining the drug susceptibility to CQ, quinine, mefloquine (MQ), halofantrine, lumefantrine, and artemisinin [42, 43]. Polymorphisms at these regions are linked with AMR and shown to reduce the efficacy of these drugs [44]. Studies show that increased copy number of *Pfmdr1* occurred due to gene duplication events which led to reduced susceptibility to lumefantrine and other partner drugs [19, 44]. Also, mutations in *P.falciparum* dihydrofolate reductase (*Pf dhfr*), *P.falciparum* dihydropteroate synthase (*Pf dhps*) were also reported to cause resistance in pyrimethamine and sulphadoxine respectively [45]. Self-medication, over the counter availability of antimalarials, negligence towards the dosage which may lead to drug resistant malaria depict the responsible factor for the increase in the antimalarials exposure and growing antimalarial resistance in Nigeria which can be seen by the increase in these genetic markers.

Plasmodium falciparum ubiquitin-specific protease 1 (*ubp1*) is a gene that influences the stability and turnover of proteins in the parasite. It plays a role in protein degradation and regulation within the parasite [46]. This is thought to be a model through which parasites can withstand the rapid action of artemisinin treatment. As such, *ubp1* polymorphism may impact the clearance of damaged or misfolded proteins and increase inception of resistance towards antimalarials [47].

2. Methodology

This review was developed from available literatures related to the spread of antimalarial resistance in Nigeria and globally. The intensive literature search was carried out by using public databases viz. Google scholar and PubMed. The search was made using the combination of keywords like, “malaria”, “antimalarial drugs”, “antimalarial resistance”, “antimalarial resistance genes”, “antimalarial abuse in Nigeria” and “one health”. The search was narrowed to articles published between 2014 to 2025. The articles providing details on each of these topics (or in combination) were filtered and used for the synthesis of this review. The review was aimed to provide the overview of the growing issue of antimalarial resistance in Nigeria from the one health approach.

2.1. Nigeria Government Initiatives to curb Malaria and Antimalarial resistance

The Nigeria Malaria Elimination Programme (NMEP) formerly called National Malaria Control Programme (NMCP) has a mandate to formulate, facilitate policy and guidelines, coordinate the activities of partners and other stakeholders on malaria elimination and control activities. It is also charged with providing technical support to implementing bodies and partners including states, Local Government Areas and stakeholders, mobilization of resources, monitoring and evaluation of progress and outcomes in malaria control efforts. It was founded in 2013 with a mission to shift malaria focus from control to elimination strategies. It has a National Malaria Strategic Plan which was developed to respond to the goal and vision of NMEP. Its main objectives are to: Improve access and utilization of vector control interventions to at least 80% of targeted population by 2025, ensure provision of chemoprevention, diagnosis and appropriate treatment for 80% of the target populations at risk by 2025. To improve generation of evidence for decision making and impact through reporting of quality malaria data and information from at least 80% of health facilities (public and private) and other data sources including surveillance, surveys and operations research by 2025. To strengthen coordination, collaboration, and strategic partnership to promote efficiency and effectiveness of malaria control activities and to improve funding for malaria control by at least 25% annually through predictable and innovative sources to ensure sustainability at federal and sub-national levels [48]. Also, the Nigeria Malaria Elimination Programme in collaboration with Malaria Consortium have come together to fight malaria and incidences of antimalarial resistance (AMR) through subsidizing and increasing

availability of quality rapid diagnostic tests (RDT) and quality antimalarial drugs. Not all fevers should be regarded as malaria fever as such only those that need malaria drugs will be given through the RDTs and gold standard malaria microscopy tests in primary, secondary and tertiary health institutions, this will help in reducing the spate of AMR being noticed now [49]. A research was carried out from 2010-2017 of having affordable antimalarial drugs but not testing initially but now seeing the effects of AMR, it has added subsidizing quality RDTs to its programmes. "The subsidy schemes at the focus of this research, Affordable Medicines Facility – malaria (AMFm) and the Private Sector Co-payment Mechanism (PSCM), were in place in Nigeria between 2010 and 2017. The schemes subsidized the cost of quality-assured artemisinin-based combination therapy (QA-ACT), the recommended first line antimalarial medicine for uncomplicated malaria, in the private sector. Nigeria was among a number of selected countries that implemented AMFm and PSCM programmes, which subsidized ACTs but not RDTs, even though both the diagnosis and treatment of malaria are integral parts of malaria case management" [49]. There was a stark low supply of RDTs as against ACTs that was almost 99% in supplies in private pharmacies and Proprietary and Patent Medicine Vendors (PPMVs) centers increasing the reach of drugs to the locals which might be one of the causes of misuse of these drugs. Malarial treatment failures and AMR may also be due to self-medication, not finishing the prescriptions given by the physicians, inappropriate dosing, fake drugs etc. In a study by carried out in Ibadan, Nigeria; 69% of respondents self-prescribed and self-managed their under 5 children believing that the drugs available in hospitals were ineffective 44.2% used antibiotics to treat empirical malaria believing it works better, 13.2% used local herb preparations called "agbo" while 12.5% used prayers. Consistent education on the effects of misuse and effects of AMR that can affect our agricultural produce, environment cannot be over-emphasized, one health approach can be used to prevent AMR when the populace understands the effects of AMR.

2.2. Drugs used in treatment of malaria in Nigeria

The National antimalarial drug Policy have recommended the use of Artemether-Lumefantrine (AL) for treating uncomplicated malaria and injectable artesunate for complicated malaria. In a study carried out in Benin, Nigeria; the level of adherence to the policy was high (78.5%) as most doctors prescribed artemether-Lumefantrine, AL for uncomplicated malaria however barely two-fifth (35.4%) adhered to prescribing injectable Artesunate for complicated malaria. The most prescribed antimalarial drugs for complicated malaria were artesunate (40.0%) followed by quinine (27.6%) and artemether (26.7%); although, chloroquine was also prescribed [50]. The training and retraining of physicians and other healthcare workers is also important as their adherence to policies was sub-optimal in this study.

In another research carried out in Ethiopia, on adherence of AL for uncomplicated malaria in malaria patients, was not quite high (53.6%) [51]. Some factors like Illiteracy (some didn't know the effect of stopping their medication when they felt better, while others saved it for other times) could be abated through appropriate educational interventions. This be a positive step in malaria and AMR control strategies. In Nigeria, ACTs are recommended by the National malaria drug policy because of the failure of CQ treatment. However, CQ is still used to treat malaria in some cases because it is both accessible and cheap. Currently, artemether-Lumefantrine (AL) and (Artesunate)AS-Amodiaquine (AQ), as the recommended antimalarial -based combinations, are adopted for the treatment of uncomplicated malaria in Nigeria, and recent therapeutic efficacy studies showed that the cure rate was more than 95% above the WHO corrected PCR value [52]. A meta-analysis by Marwa *et al.*, in sub-Saharan Africa shows that the therapeutic efficacy studies of AL was 89%, AS-AQ 94% and dihydroartemisinin-piperazine 91% but after PCR correction, it was 98%, 99% and 99% respectively [53]. At present, pregnant Nigerian women are also recommended to receive 3+ doses of SP to prevent malaria [54]. In some parts of Nigeria like Ibadan, Edo and Ekiti there are reports of treatments of suspected malaria cases with antimalarials at sub-optimal doses, non-compliance of caregivers amounting to 80% of children under 5 inappropriately treated by home-based caregivers with only about 15% of care actions being correct [55, 56]. These actions can increase the malaria parasite development of resistance due to the sub-optimal doses; also, our tropical settings favour the genotypic diversity of the parasite across different individuals, populations and seasons in malaria endemic zones [57]. So regular monitoring of anti-malarial drug efficacy is crucial in detecting antimalarial resistance and also in forming national treatment guidelines thus ensuring effective treatment outcomes [2, 3, 52].

3. Discussion

Malaria has been a significant infection raising economic concerns in Nigerian families. Antimalarial drug resistance is increasing now especially with inappropriate dosing, wrong composition and mutations of the endemic strain *Plasmodium falciparum*. A study carried out in Henan, China from 2012 to 2019 on imported *P.falciparum* isolates from Nigeria showed that there were antimalarial drug-resistant genes and mutants, like *PfK13*, *Pfcr1*, *Pfmdr1*, *Pfdhfr*, and *Pfdhps*. Among the 167 imported *P. falciparum* isolates, the wild-type frequency of *PfK13*, *Pfcr1*, *Pfmdr1*, *Pfdhfr*, and *Pfdhps* were 98.7, 63.9, 34.8, 3.1, and 3.1%, respectively. The mutation of *PfK13* was rare, with just two nonsynonymous (S693F and Q613H) and two synonymous mutations (C469C and G496G) identified from four isolates [58]. The prevalence of *Pfcr1* mutation at codon 74–76 decreased year-by-year, while the prevalence of *pfmdr1* 86Y also decreased significantly with time but the prevalence of *Pfdhfr* and *Pfdhps* mutants were high. This indicates that some mutants are still prone to causing high diversities of the parasite that can increase infection rates [58] this shows that the emergence and spread of ACT resistance represents a significant threat to malaria prevention and control. Resistance to antimalarials have been linked to chloroquine, sulfadoxine- pyrimethamine, mefloquine, quinine and now the ACT drugs [55]. ACTs were recommended by the WHO due to these insensitivities [WHO, 2015] but of recent there have been reports of resistance to even the ACTs. Factors like polymorphisms of the parasite, parasite load, parasite mutation rate, treatment compliance, strength of drug selected, not adhering to antimalarial drug guidelines, wrong dosing of drug, counterfeit drug without proper active pharmaceutical ingredients (API) leading to inadequate drug exposure on parasites may favour resistance properties of the parasite predisposing to hyperparasitaemia and recrudescence [2, 17, 59, 60].

Self-medication is also one of the attributing factors of antimalarial drug resistance as some caregivers, parents might not know the correct dosing or be responsible enough to complete the dosing once patient feels a little better, with risk of drug abuse that can bring about the emergence and spread of antimalarial and even antimicrobial resistance [27]. The use of drugs for preventable issues without testing and prescription accounts for more than 50% of preventable harm [16]. A systems approach and safe prescription practices e.g. collecting the prescription sheet after giving the patient medications can be utilized to prevent people from buying drugs over the counter without professional advice or even counterfeit pharmaceuticals as they abound in Africa [16].

Measures to Curb Antimalarial Resistance

The National Malaria Elimination Programme poised with the duty of making policies to ensure that malaria and antimalarials are working effectively should ensure that there is adequate monitoring, evaluation and therapeutic efficacy studies of available antimalarials. Regulatory agencies should ensure there are efficient testing kits for investigations of the various parasite strains especially the most virulent strain *P.falciparum* and *P.vivax* that are more prone to resistance than the other strains [2, 3, 58]. Recently some novel antimalarials are undergoing trials called the triple ACTs; having artemisinin derivative and two partner drugs working in different ways is on study having promises to reduce the risk of resistance [2, 17]. Discovery of novel biochemical pathways in the malaria parasite will bring about opportunities for development of novel antimalarials that will target organelles specific to the parasite e.g. the apicoplast genome [17], the var2csa gene can block malaria parasites protein switching disabling their immune evasion tactics [41]. Several new drugs; the new synthetic endoperoxides e.g. OZ439 and artefenomel are some trial drugs having some promise to prevent resistance in the parasites. So are aminoquinolines like ferroquine, cipargamin, DSM265 and MMV390048 are inhibitors of important parasite enzymes [2, 61, 62].

Use of alternatives

The World Health Organization have advocated that malaria endemic countries use alternative measures to chemotherapy to reduce resistance. This use of alternatives to drugs like encouraging the use of long-lasting insecticide treated nets, carrying out regular public health education to the masses on the effects of malaria, use of indoor residual spray, larvicidal source management, keeping our environment clean devoid of stagnant waters that breed the vector *Anopheles gambiae* [16].

Modern electronic data management system can be applied to help in fast tracking monitoring and surveillance of analysis of malaria and genetic data for effective utilization and allocation of our scarce health commodities. The global malaria partners have been in support and the support is still advocated to control this menace. This will help to monitor resistance against malaria and government can adapt its strategies effectively [24].

Simple messages on effects of dirty environments, not complying with your drugs or not finishing your dosage should be thought regularly in various settings like markets, schools, churches as jingles, posters, radio and television programme, social media etc. to educate the populace on the dangers of malaria and AMR. The use of directly observed treatment (DOT) where a healthcare worker or community volunteer makes sure the patient complies with his medication is also a method that can work in the rural areas but in the urban part of Nigeria educating the populace regularly will be a better option to mitigate the risk of resistance development [63]. More research and development are necessary for health workers, especially on drug analysis as resistance can have a one health approach; can affect the environment, animals that feed on the environment and humans that feed on animals. The knowledge of these can help in curbing the development of resistance genes in man [14].

4. Conclusion

The emergence and spread of antimalarial drug resistance is a major threat to the management and control of malaria that if not properly handled globally could reverse the progress of the world malaria containment programs. The right use of antimalarials cannot be overemphasized considering our malaria-endemic region and to prevent antimalarial resistance so that what we have can work for us. Improving access to malaria prevention and treatment services is essential, particularly in rural areas where many people lack adequate healthcare access. Training healthcare workers in these areas will ensure proper diagnosis and treatment, thus reducing the burden of malaria and resistance to antimalarial drugs available currently This can be achieved through the expansion of distribution channels for insecticide-treated bed nets, quality diagnostic tests, quality antimalarial drugs, training patients on how to comply with their medications and the dangers of AMR. Apart from educating healthcare professionals, one health approach should also be encouraged by also training agriculturists, farmers, environmentalists on the effects of AMR. Strict legislation on quality pharmaceuticals for pharmacies and pharmaceutical companies should be prioritized. Identification of newly emerged malarial strains different from those in the genomic database, prioritizing research on AMR, local awareness of the dangers of AMR, completing the dose of antimalarials even after feeling better have to be taught to the locals to understand the dangers of AMR hence mitigating the global effect of malaria and antimalarial resistance.

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